

Combining artificial neural networks with finite element methods to predict the structural response of the proximal femur

A.I. Pais¹, J.L. Alves^{1,2} and J. Belinha^{1,3}

¹ INEGI - Institute of Science and Innovation in Mechanical and Industrial Engineering, Porto, Portugal, ana.i.pais@gmail.com

² Department of Mechanical Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, University of Porto (FEUP), Porto, Portugal, falves@fe.up.pt

³ Department of Mechanical Engineering, School of Engineering, Polytechnic of Porto (ISEP), Porto, Portugal, job@isep.ipp.pt

Abstract

The finite element method (FEM) is a highly popular discretization numerical technique in computational mechanics. However, nowadays, numerical applications are becoming increasingly complex. Thus, traditional solving techniques generally demand a larger computational capacity and show higher computational costs. Machine learning techniques can be combined with the FEM to reduce the computational cost associated with the numerical analysis, being applied as surrogate solvers or as a predictive tool. This work presents a brief introduction to feed forward neural networks, a machine learning technique, using MATLAB[®] with a first benchmark example of a classification problem, the "two moons" problem, with the objective of introducing the most important concepts. This first example allowed to understand the basic machine artificial learning with neural networks (NN) MATLAB[®] tools. Then, a second problem was analysed with the objective of showing the potential of combining FEM with artificial NN for a biomechanical application. It was observed that the artificial NN allow to predict displacements and stresses with a high level of accuracy and, simultaneously, save a significant computational time. Surprisingly, feature analysis through connection weights approach on the input variables showed that the neural network was capable of detecting the physical importance of the variables for each problem. The most significant disadvantage of artificial NN is the necessity of acquiring large amounts of data and prepare such data for training and testing, which is time consuming.

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1 Introduction

The finite element method (FEM) is a powerful numerical technique, which has allowed the acceleration of mechanical design and research since its creation. However, with the growing complexity of the mechanical systems under analysis, systems with often millions of unknowns must be solved which requires a great deal of computational power and computing time.

Artificial intelligence (AI), a branch of computer science that develops machines and software with human-like intelligence, is proving to be an efficient alternative approach to classical modelling techniques [1, 2]. The AI, using artificial neural networks (NN), the core technique of deep learning (DL), has already been tested and applied in relevant computational mechanics fields [1, 3]. Artificial NN can be classified by their architectural structure as "feed forward neural networks" or "mutually connected neural networks" [1]. ML uses training data to learn and develop models, which later can deliver trends and predictions [3]. More, since artificial NN are capable of nonlinear mapping, NN are suitable to provide a solution for multi-variable problems in a fraction of time, when compared with conventional computational methodologies [1].

Figure 1: Artificial Neural Network architecture

Recently, there has been growing interest in the application of artificial neural networks in the field of computational mechanics [1], for example in computational homogenization of random heterogeneous materials [4], in the constitutive modelling of composites [5], in the prediction of the stress fields of solid mechanics benchmarks [6], in non-linear structural analysis [7], and in the field of biomechanics for example to predict body posture, [8, 9, 10], modelling the properties of scaffolds [11] and predicting the mechanical response and load in long bones [12, 13].

This work uses the in-house MATLAB[®] function *feedforwardnet*. The *feedforwardnet* and other functions mentioned in this manuscript are included in the *Deep Learning Toolbox* of MATLAB[®]. The first example shown in this work introduces the most important concepts and functions. The second analysed problem shows an application of artificial neural networks in the field of computational biomechanics.

1.1 Artificial neural networks

Figure 1 shows a scheme of a simple neural network. Any hidden or output node consists of a non-linear transformation f of the values of the nodes in the previous layer. This transformation is the weighted sum of the inputs passed through a non linear activation function, and is shown in equation (1)

$$z = f(b + \mathbf{x}^T \cdot \mathbf{w}) = f\left(b + \sum_{i=1}^m x_i \cdot w_i\right) \quad (1)$$

where b is the bias, x_i is the value from the node i in the previous layer and w_i is the weight corresponding to that node. It is the training process of the network that allows to obtain the values for the weights and bias.

Some examples of activation functions include the sigmoid function:

$$f(\Sigma) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-\Sigma}} \quad (2)$$

and the hyperbolic tangent:

$$f(\Sigma) = \frac{e^{+\Sigma} - e^{-\Sigma}}{e^{+\Sigma} + e^{-\Sigma}} \quad (3)$$

where Σ is, according to equation 1, the weighted sum of the nodes from the previous layer [14]. The final network is therefore able to perform some non-linear transformation and create decision boundaries capable of accurately classifying complex sets of data. In order to determine the accuracy of the neural network predictions, the mean squared error (MSE) calculates the difference between the target vector and the output vector according to equation 4,

$$MSE = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m (t_i - y_i)^2 \quad (4)$$

where t_i is the element of the target vector and y_i is the prediction made by the neural network for the same inputs that

Figure 2: Schematic representation of the classification problem with the decision boundary (a) and dataset used for the training of the neural network (b)

originate the target t_i . The differences are squared in order to make sure that negative differences are not subtracted from positive ones [14]. Different accuracy metrics can be used, such as the mean absolute error (MAE) and mean absolute percentage error (MAPE). In a neural network training there are two different propagation moments, forward propagation where data goes from the input layer to the output layer (thus giving a prediction or classification), and backward propagation, which allows to train the network. In backward propagation data does the reverse transformation in order to determine the error and adjust the weights and bias by minimizing the cost function, which can be the MSE or any other function [14]. Each passing of data forwards and backwards through the network is called an *epoch*, thus, an *epoch* consists of using the training data only once. An *epoch* can consist on one or more iterations depending on whether the *batch size* is the same as the size of the training data. There are several algorithms to adjust the weights, which must be chosen according to the type of problem being analysed, whether the artificial neural network aims at solving a regression problem or a classification problem. The main difference between the two tasks is that a classification problem predicts a label and a regression problem predicts a quantity.

2 Methodology

2.1 Two-moons

The first example is a simple "two moons" classification example. In this example it is not possible to use a linear regression model to accurately classify the points, as the boundary between the two moon is not linear, as it can be observed in Figure 2(a). Figure 2(b) shows the training data for the "two moons" example. The input data consists on the coordinates of the point: x_1 and x_2 , and the colour of each moon is the output label of the classification problem, which is going to be represented as -1 for blue and 1 for red.

The full code is shown next and it is going to be explained line by line afterwards.

```

1 clc
2 clear all
3 load('2Moons_sets.mat')
4 inputs = x';
5 targets = y';
6 untrained_net = feedforwardnet([4,3]);
7 view(untrained_net)
8 [trained_net,tr] = train(untrained_net,inputs,targets);

```

The previous code builds in line 6 a neural network with an input layer, two hidden layers, each with 4 and 3 nodes, respectively, and the output layer. The number of nodes in the input and output layer is inferred from the dimension of the

Figure 3: Result of the `view` function (a) untrained (b) trained.

arrays used and inputs and targets in line 8 when the network is trained. Because the "two-moons" dataset is not linearly separable, two hidden layers are used. If more hidden layers were used, overfitting problems are likely to occur. In Figure 3(a) it is possible to observe the output from the `view net` function, where it can be seen that at that stage it is still not possible to know how many nodes are at the input and output, as it indicates zero nodes. Moreover, it is possible to visualise that, by default, the transfer function in the hidden layers is a symmetric sigmoid transfer function, or *tanh* function and in the output layer we have a *'purelin'* function. This means that after the last hidden layer a linear transformation is performed, and that the input to that layer equals the output. Table 1 shows a list of available activation functions. In line 8, the `train` function will display the network with the correct number of nodes as can be seen in Figure 3(b).

Table 1: List of possible activation functions

Name of the function	Description
<i>'compet'</i>	Competitive transfer function
<i>'elliotsig'</i>	Elliot sigmoid transfer function
<i>'hardlim'</i>	Positive hard limit transfer function
<i>'hardlims'</i>	Symmetric hard limit transfer function
<i>'logsig'</i>	Logarithmic sigmoid transfer function
<i>'netinv'</i>	Inverse transfer function
<i>'poslin'</i>	Positive linear transfer function
<i>'purelin'</i>	Linear transfer function
<i>'radbas'</i>	Radial basis transfer function
<i>'radbasn'</i>	Radial basis normalized transfer function
<i>'satlin'</i>	Positive saturating linear transfer function
<i>'satlins'</i>	Symmetric saturating linear transfer function
<i>'softmax'</i>	Soft max transfer function
<i>'tansig'</i>	Symmetric sigmoid transfer function (by default)
<i>'tribas'</i>	Triangular basis transfer function

The `network` function is another MATLAB[®] function, which creates custom neural networks. The following code generates, using the `network` function, a neural network `net2` with the same architecture as `net1`.

```

1 net1 = feedforwardnet([4,3]);
2 view(net1)
3 net2 = network(1,3,[1;1;1],[1;0;0],[0 0 0;1 0 0;0 1 0],[0 0 1]);
4 net2.layers{1}.size = 4;
5 net2.layers{2}.size = 3;
6 net2.layers{1:2}.transferFcn = 'tansig';
7 view(net2);

```

The output of both the *feedforwardnet* or *network* function is an object of type *net*. Nevertheless, if the objective is to create a fully connected feed forward network, using the *feedforwardnet* allows to use less lines of code.

A second input in the *feedforwardnet* function, which was omitted in the example, is the training function. If omitted, this parameter assumes the '*trainlm*' function, which is the Levenberg-Marquardt training function. Another common training function is the "gradient descent". If one wishes for the network to be trained this way, it must be indicated in the second input of the function as '*traingd*'. A list of available training functions is shown in Table 2. The most appropriate training function will depend on the characteristics of the problem at study.

Table 2: List of available training functions in the *feedforwardnet* function

Input in the function	Training function name
' <i>trainlm</i> '	Levenberg-Marquardt (used by default)
' <i>trainbr</i> '	Bayesian Regularization
' <i>trainbfg</i> '	BFGS Quasi-Newton
' <i>trainrpf</i> '	Resilient Backpropagation
' <i>trainscg</i> '	Scaled Conjugate Gradient
' <i>traingb</i> '	Conjugate Gradient with Powell/Beale Restarts
' <i>traingf</i> '	Fletcher-Powell Conjugate Gradient
' <i>traingcp</i> '	Polak-Ribière Conjugate Gradient
' <i>trainoss</i> '	One Step Secant
' <i>traingdx</i> '	Variable Learning Rate Gradient Descent
' <i>traingdm</i> '	Gradient Descent with Momentum
' <i>traingd</i> '	Gradient Descent

The final step consists of the training of the network, which is achieved by means of the function *train*, also available in the *Deep Learning Toolbox*.

Additionally, it is important to perform data normalisation before the training process, in order to obtain a mean close to zero (which will lead to faster learning and convergence). Data normalisation will allow the data to be dimensionless or to present similar distributions within different data sets. Next, two examples of data normalisation are shown. The first, where the *mapminmax* function is used in order to scale the inputs and targets to fall within the $[-1, 1]$ range, and the second, where the *mapstd* function is used, normalising the data by transforming the mean and standard deviation to 0 and 1, respectively. In lines 4 to 6 of the examples, it is shown how to transform the test data according to the parameters in the training data.

```

1 [n_inputs,ps_inputs] = mapminmax(inputs);
2 [n_targets,ps_targets] = mapminmax(targets);
3 [trnet_n,tr_n] = train(net,n_inputs,n_targets);
4 test_data_n = mapminmax('apply',test_data,ps_inputs);
5 test_target_n = net(test_data_n);
6 test_target = mapminmax('reverse',test_target_n,ps_targets);

```

```

1 [n_inputs,ps_inputs] = mapstd(inputs);
2 [n_targets,ps_targets] = mapstd(targets);
3 [trnet_n,tr_n] = train(net,n_inputs,n_targets);
4 test_data_n = mapstd('apply',test_data,ps_inputs);
5 test_target_n = net(test_data_n);
6 test_target = mapstd('reverse',test_target_n,ps_targets);

```

Due to the nature of the "two moons" classification problem, the first approach is chosen. Lastly, the test data is shown next, in Figure 4. Test data 1 changes the two moons configuration, while test data 2 consists of points within the two moons used in the training set, only slightly changing the points coordinates. The difference between all data sets are more easily

Figure 4: Test data without normalization

understood in Figure 5, which shows that test set 1 is largely different from the training set, while test set 2 is very similar, as both sets are almost completely overlapping in the scatter plot.

However, the *feedforwardnet* function has by default some data pre-processing procedures, such as cleaning constant rows and data normalisation using the *mapminmax*. Thus, the data normalisation step will do nothing, as the input is already normalised. Nevertheless, doing this previous data normalisation step provides the normalisation parameters *ps_inouts* and *ps_targets* so that when testing with different datasets the data can be fed to the net with the correct format.

Because the size of the input layer is 2, it is possible to visualise the decision boundary obtained by the training of the neural network. In order to have a visual representation of the decision boundary, the following code aids in the visualisation of the trained boundary, where the coordinates of points defined in a mesh grid are passed through the trained network and thus, the output will be a colour map showing the output of the network for all points in space.

```

1 increment = 0.01; %resolution of the meshgrid
2 xx = min(n_inputs(1,:)):increment:max(n_inputs(1,:));
3 yy = min(n_inputs(2,:)):increment:max(n_inputs(2,:));
4 [X,Y] = meshgrid(xx,yy);
5 grid_coordinates = [X(:), Y(:)]';
6 final = trnet_n(grid_coordinates);
7 hold on
8 colormap('jet');
9 scatter(grid_coordinates(1,:)',grid_coordinates(2,:)',25,final,'filled');
10 scatter(n_inputs(1,n_targets==-1)',n_inputs(2,n_targets==-1)',25,'white','filled');
11 scatter(n_inputs(1,n_targets==1)',n_inputs(2,n_targets==1)',25,'black','filled');
12 colorbar;

```

2.2 Displacements and normal stresses in the proximal femur (2D analysis)

The second studied problem is a 2D analysis of the proximal femur. In section 2.1, the concepts relevant to the coding of this problem were already presented in previous sections, so this section will only show the variables and network architecture. The input and output variables are shown in Figure 6(a), and 6(b) shows the meaning of such variables. Therefore, P_1 is any random point located in the greater trochanter and P_2 is any random point approximately in the centre of the femur head. In this problem, the objective is to predict the normal stresses σ_{xx} and σ_{yy} at the proximal diaphysis, and displacements u_x and u_y in the femoral head. The variables h and $P_1P_2(l)$ quantify size differences in the model, height and width respectively, and θ accounts for the model distortions. The test and training data were obtained using FEM analysis on models of 13

Figure 5: Comparison of the training set and the test sets

different geometries by applying different scales to the x and y axes, and 19 different combinations of angles at which the loads are applied. The magnitude of F_2 was defined as being $F_2 = 0.3 \times F_1$, and F_1 is enough that the material reaches its elastic limit. The model which was used to gather the training and test data is discretized with 3300 nodes and 3150 quadrilateral elements. The elastic modulus considered for the model is $E = 33$ GPa and the Poisson's coefficient is $\nu = 0.3$. The use of data standardisation is highlighted in this example because human bones present geometrical and dimensional differences from individual to individual. Thus, the data is mapped using the *mapstd* function because human properties will usually follow a normal probability distribution. This will transform each input and output variable so that the mean μ is 0 and the standard deviation σ^2 is 1.

A total of $n_{instances} = 152$ analyses were run in order to obtain the necessary data. First, the simulation files were read and summarised into a table containing all the inputs and outputs named *all_data* with the following structure:

$$\begin{array}{cccccccc}
 h & \overline{P_1 P_2}(l) & \theta & \alpha & \beta & u_x & u_y & \sigma_{xx} & \sigma_{yy} \\
 \dots & \dots
 \end{array}$$

so the inputs correspond to the first 5 columns of the table and the targets correspond to the last four columns of the table. Additionally, the data is standardised so that each variable has mean $\mu = 0$ and standard deviation $\sigma^2 = 1$.

```

1 %normalizing the data for the training of the network
2 inputs = data(:,1:5);
3 ux = data(:,6); %horizontal displacement
4 uy = data(:,7); %horizontal displacement
5 sxx = data(:,8); %normal stress xx
6 syy = data(:,9); %normal stress yy
7 [inputs_n,ps_inputs] = mapstd(inputs');
8 [ux_n,ps_ux] = mapstd(ux(:,1)'); %standardizing the horizontal displacement
9 [uy_n,ps_uy] = mapstd(uy(:,1)'); %standardizing the vertical displacement
10 [sxx_n,ps_sxx] = mapstd(sxx(:,1)'); %standardizing the normal stress xx
11 [syy_n,ps_syy] = mapstd(syy(:,1)'); %standardizing the normal stress yy

```

For this problem the network architecture used in both cases consists of a two layered network, the hidden layer with 20 nodes and the output layer with one node for the output. Figure 7 shows the network used in both cases. The activation function used in the hidden layer was the symmetric sigmoid (*tansig*) and the output layer also consisted of a linear transformation, where the input equals the output. Similarly to the first problem, the training function defined by default is used, which is the *trainlm* function. During the training process, 106 of the samples are used in the training, 23 samples are used in validation and 23 samples are used in the testing. The samples used in the training were chosen randomly from the training data. Additionally, 12 samples which had never been used were used to test the accuracy of the network. These 12 samples all present the same distortion but vary between themselves the α and β parameters.

Figure 6: Problem summary (a) input and output variables (b) variable scheme

Figure 7: Network architecture used to obtain the displacements d_x and d_y and the normal stresses σ_{xx} and σ_{yy}

Figure 8: Distribution of the standardized variables (a) input and (b) target

The training procedure requires weight initialisation, which shows a heavy influence in the final training result of the neural network. In order to achieve the best possible weight initialisation, the network was initialised and trained N times. The final network corresponds to the initialisation which provided the lower mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) with the 12 additional samples, which had not been seen by the network. The MAPE is given by

$$MAPE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n \left| \frac{A_t - P_t}{A_t} \right| \quad (5)$$

where A_t is the actual value, calculated through the FEM and P_t is the predicted value from the artificial neural network. The N value was determined iteratively until the network with the best performance showed a maximum relative error lower than 10% within the 12 samples not previously seen by the network, starting N at $N = 1000$ with increments of 1000. The network initialisation (only for the horizontal displacement, it is the same for the remaining networks) and training is showed next

```
1 targets_n = ux_n;
2 net_ux = feedforwardnet(20);
3 [tr_net_ux,param_ux] = train(net_ux,inputs_n,targets_n);
```

Because the network takes the normalised inputs, the same normalisation parameters are used for the 12 example samples. Having obtained the results from the network, it is necessary to revert the normalisation of the output array.

```
1 ins_test = [h;P1P2_l;theta;alpha;beta];%inputs for the test case
2 ins_n = mapstd('apply',ins_test,ps_inputs); %normalized inputs
3 ux_n_test = tr_net_ux(ins_n); %normalized horizontal displacement output
4 uy_n_test = tr_net_uy(ins_n); %normalized vertical displacement output
5 sxx_n_test = tr_net_sxx(ins_n); %normalized normal stress xx output
6 syy_n_test = tr_net_syy(ins_n); %normalized normal stress yy output
7 ux = mapstd('reverse',ux_n_test,ps_ux); %unscaled horizontal displacement
8 uy = mapstd('reverse',uy_n_test,ps_uy); %unscaled horizontal displacement
9 sxx = mapstd('reverse',sxx_n_test,ps_sxx); %unscaled normal stress xx
10 syy = mapstd('reverse',syy_n_test,ps_syy); %unscaled normal stress yy
```

The distribution of the standardised input and target variables used in the training of this example is shown in Figure 8.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Two-moons

Figure 10(a) shows an example of a run of the trained network on two different test sets. It should be noted that the data division done in the training takes a default data division and weight initialisation and, therefore, the results should change

Figure 9: (a) Example of the trained network on two different test sets and (b) Decision boundary for normalised inputs on the training dataset

Table 3: Performance comparison between the artificial neural networks and the reference results, obtained through the FEM

	best net (s)	total training (s)	prediction time (s)	FEM time (s)	MAPE	necessary runs
u_x	1.199	1110.135	1.374	30	1.63%	1000
u_y	1.807	1635.129	1.374	30	1.62%	1000
σ_{xx}	1.627	9269.034	1.374	30	5.20%	5000
σ_{yy}	2.578	2452.89	1.374	30	3.90%	1000

every time the code is run.

Since test set 2 is quite similar to the training set, where the point coordinates differ within the same range of the training data set, the network had 100% precision. On the other hand, test set 1 changes the two moons configuration quite a lot and, therefore, 20.5% of the points are misclassified. The decision boundary obtained is shown in Figure 10(b) for the normalised inputs. The points classified with 1 are marked in black and the points classified with -1 are marked in white.

3.2 Displacement and stress in the proximal femur

The results of the trained networks for each of the displacements and stresses are shown in Figure 10. First, it is shown the MSE plotted along the epochs, as well as the absolute percentage error (APE) given by

$$APE = \left| \frac{P_t - A_t}{A_t} \right| \tag{6}$$

along for each of the 12 samples that the network did not see during the training.

Analysing the regression plots (which correlate the predicted outputs with the correct target value), it can be seen that all the displacements were correctly predicted as well as the normal stress σ_{yy} .

It is possible to visualise that with enough tries, the weight initialisation provided errors that are acceptable bellow 10%. More, from Table 3, which shows how the artificial neural network compares to the FEM performance, it is possible to visualise how a well trained neural network outperforms the FEM in terms of computational time with satisfactory accuracy. Due to the fact that the training data has a relatively small size, the training of one network took, in some cases, a lower time than the prediction. The small amount of data, conjugated with the randomness of the weight initialisation algorithm, led to a high number of tries. Such number was required in order to get a neural network with good enough performance.

Figure 10: Performance results of the networks with the best performance (a) displacement at the femoral head (b) normal stresses at the diaphysis

Table 4: Importance of each variable using the connection weight approach by Olden et al. [15]

	u_x		u_y		σ_{xx}		σ_{yy}	
	importance	rank	importance	rank	importance	rank	importance	rank
h	0.062400554	5	-1.415369025	3	-0.489007928	3	0.553022086	5
l	0.837122148	4	0.08092881	4	0.893937726	2	-0.657534966	4
θ	2.847490417	1	-0.072197728	5	2.162784543	1	-0.732870909	3
α	-1.433177231	2	-6.012677872	1	0.273148366	4	-8.961103865	1
β	-1.195840853	3	-3.15426349	2	-0.08160777	5	-3.403068005	2

Consequently, the total training time increased drastically. For example, in the work of Mouloudi et al. [12] (who worked on displacement), experimental data was used to predict load and strain. This work showed the amount of data that is required in order to train the artificial neural network so it presents a low error [12].

Nevertheless, it was possible to train the network to an acceptable level of error. Even though the stresses and displacements are only required at two points of the model, the complex shape of the femur requires FEM analysis in order to output those variables. The trained artificial neural network thus provides good enough data so that the FEM step can be abandoned when calculating such a small number of parameters.

Finally, it is possible to assess the importance of each variable for the calculation of the output, for each variable, using the approach by Olden et al. [15]. This is done by multiplying the matrix of connections weights between the input and hidden layer W_I with the matrix of connection weights between the hidden and the output layer W_O . W_I is $[N_{in} \times M]$, where M is the number of neurons in the hidden layer and N_{in} is the number of neurons in the input layer and W_O is $[M \times N_o]$ where N_o is the number of outputs. The result is

$$I = W_I \cdot W_O \quad (7)$$

which is $[N_{in} \times N_o]$ and consists in the importance that each input variable has for the output result. A negative sign signifies a negative correlation of the input variable with the output. Table 4 ranks the variables. Olden's approach shows some advantages in comparison to other feature selection approaches, as it also provides information regarding the excitation or inhibition effect of a variable.

Due to the specificity of each problem, each neural network relies differently on different features. Because the magnitude of the force applied to the femoral head is higher than the magnitude of the force applied to the greater trochanter, it is expected, considering the physical explanation of the problem, that α would consistently rank higher than β in variable importance, which was verified. It would be interesting to re-run the training procedure and to each network omit the variables with the least or very low importance. Other differences may be due to the dataset used in the analysis.

4 Conclusion

In conclusion, this work shows that a large amount of computational time can be saved through the use of artificial neural networks, especially for models with a large number of nodes where the computational time increases drastically. However, large amounts of data must be acquired in order to have a quality approximation from the neural network. Moreover, the significance analysis of the input features allowed to conclude that even though artificial intelligence is often a "black box" approach, the neural network was capable to capture the physical meaning of the problem, as the most important variables for each case are in agreement with the expectations developed from the mechanics of the problem. Finally, it was shown that the network was capable of solving both classification and regression problems.

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